

DELAMINATION-SUPPRESSION CONCEPTS FOR COMPOSITE LAMINATE FREE EDGES

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ABSTRACT

Some fiber-reinforced composite laminates have a strong tendency to delaminate near edges that are unloaded and unsupported, i.e., free edges. This type of delamination significantly reduces static strength as well as fatigue life of such laminates, but has essentially no influence on stiffness. Edge reinforcement and edge modification concepts to reduce the delamination tendency are shown to have good potential for significantly increasing both static strength and fatigue life of delamination-susceptible laminates. Such concepts also extend the useful range of acceptable stress levels in fatigue by delaying the onset of delamination.

KEY WORDS: Delamination; Edge Effect; Failure, interlaminar; Fatigue; Strength.

1. INTRODUCTION

A problem unique to laminated materials is the possibility of delamination under loading in the plane of the laminate, i.e., not perpendicular to the loading. For example, a laminate with a hole cut through its thickness can delaminate near the hole even without through-the-thickness loading. This three-dimensional problem is very difficult to analyze, but a simpler problem exists: some laminates with free edges have a strong tendency to delaminate near the edges when subjected to axial in-plane loading as in Figure 1. This type of delamination significantly reduces static strength as well as fatigue life of such laminates. However, the laminate extensional stiffness is essentially unaffected by the delamination that occurs only in a very narrow boundary layer about one laminate thickness wide near the free edge in Figure 2. The so-called interlaminar normal and shear stresses, σ_z , τ_{xz} , and τ_{yz} in Figure 3, that cause delamination are not considered in classical lamination theory. Interlaminar stresses are caused either by a Poisson's ratio mismatch between adjacent laminae or by shear-extension coupling between dissimilarly oriented laminae. These interlaminar stresses are very high (perhaps even "singular") near the laminate free edge in the narrow boundary layer.

Figure 1 Free-Edge Delamination

The three major types of crack propagation are the opening mode (mode I), the forward shear mode (mode II), and the parallel shear mode (mode III). The opening mode is a response to normal stress perpendicular to the plane of the crack in Figure 3. The forward shear mode is a response to shear stress parallel to the plane of the original crack. In the parallel shear mode, the crack propagates because of high shear stress acting perpendicular to the plane of the specimen.

Figure 2 The Free-Edge Effect is a Boundary-Layer Phenomenon

Figure 3 Modes of Crack Propagation Near Laminate Free Edges

This paper is a compilation of results obtained with the author in various theses and senior project reports over nearly a ten-year period. The work of other investigators is also reviewed to complete the survey of the delamination-suppression concepts shown in Figure 4. There, two major types of delamination-suppression concepts are shown: (1) free edges can be *reinforced* to make them stronger and (2) the laminate at or near the free edge can be *modified* to change the stresses that would otherwise cause delamination.

O'Brien [1] has shown that the predominant failure mode for laminate free edges is mode I delamination, i.e., delamination due to high interlaminar normal stress σ_z . Thus, wrapping a U-shaped cap around the edge of a laminate before loading such as in Figure 4 has the possibility of restraining the most significant stress causing delamination and, hence, increasing strength and fatigue life. Kim [2] wrapped the edges of graphite-epoxy laminates with fiberglass cloth and found that delaminations could be delayed or prevented. His experiments coincided with the author's initial theoretical studies. Alternatively, free-edge delamination for some laminates could be governed by the interlaminar shear stress τ_{xz} , i.e., mode III delamination. Finally, both modes could be active in the so-called mixed-mode

fracture. Some have felt that damage tolerance of composite laminates could be improved by using toughened matrix materials, and, under static loading, they are correct. However, under the more practically important situation of fatigue loading, toughened matrix materials lead to very little improvement [3].

• **EDGE REINFORCEMENT**

• **EDGE MODIFICATION**

Figure 4 Delamination-Suppression Concepts for Composite Laminate Free Edges

Reinforcing and/or modifying the free edge are simply ways of decreasing the interlaminar stresses so the strength and life of the composite laminate hopefully increase. We change the stress field in the vicinity of the free edge to weaken the singularity in the (incorrect) mathematical model of the composite laminate. The model is incorrect because the layers cannot behave in a linear elastic manner to infinitely high stresses. More simplistically, we change the stress field enough to be able to accommodate the stresses with a new configuration much more easily than without that reinforcement or modification. The concept of reinforcing or modifying free edges to prevent delamination is attractive because it allows a designer the flexibility to choose laminate stacking sequences without being concerned about free-edge effects. Although we will be concerned only with flat tensile specimens in this paper, many of these reinforcement techniques could be applied to any laminates with free edges, such as plates or shells with holes or cutouts. In addition to improving static strength and prolonging fatigue life, we would often like to eliminate delaminations because they can act as paths for moisture (or other fluid) intrusion during service life.

Concepts of edge reinforcement and edge modification to reduce the delamination tendency are investigated in this paper. Practical reinforcement concepts include simply putting a U-shaped cap around the free edge or perhaps stitching near the free edge to provide some transverse stiffness as in Figure 4. That is, *put fibers in the direction where the laminate does not have them*. On the vertical surface of the edge cap, fibers are placed in the direction perpendicular to the plane of the laminate. The laminate has fibers all in one plane and in no other direction. Yet a third possible edge reinforcement is to interleave adhesive layers between the composite laminae to provide a compliant medium between the layers with highly different fiber orientations. Aside from edge reinforcement, edge modification is possible. That is, change the makeup of the laminate near the free edge to alter the stress state. Approaches such as ply termination, notching, and tapering in Figure 4 achieve that goal. Ply termination can be viewed as a form of tapering, although the tapering shown in Figure 4 is accomplished by machining.

The objective of this paper is to explore the viability of each of the delamination-suppression concepts in Figure 4 except for machined-edge tapering. Simple delamination-prone graphite-epoxy laminates under static and/or fatigue loading are the vehicle for evaluating each concept. Current results are discussed, and improvements for future studies are suggested.

2. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The experimental results consist of five separate studies of free-edge delamination suppression. First, the basic effect of the edge-cap reinforcing concept is examined with single-layered edge caps. Included are the influence of matrix material aging and fiber orientation in the cap. Second, the interleaved adhesive layer concept is evaluated. Third, edge stitching is addressed to assess its effect on delamination suppression. Fourth, laminate plies are terminated near the free edge to gain a different effect. Fifth, the influence of edge notching is explored.

2.1 Effect of Edge Caps In the first study of edge caps, fifteen symmetric eleven-layer graphite-epoxy [$\pm 30^\circ_2/90^\circ_3/\pm 30^\circ_2$] laminates, NASA edge-delamination tension specimens, with a one-layer cap of Kevlar-epoxy cloth were loaded to failure [4,5]. Of these 15 specimens, eight had edge caps with one layer of $0^\circ/90^\circ$ Kevlar-epoxy cloth. Three of the capped specimens were loaded in static tension, and five were loaded in tension-tension fatigue. Of the seven remaining specimens, four were loaded in static tension, and three were loaded in fatigue. For both the static and fatigue loadings, the capped specimens were significantly stronger than the uncapped specimens. The addition of edge caps to the static-test specimens also greatly decreased the coefficient of variation of the static strength. Kim previously reported prevention or delay of delamination with edge wrapping [2].

Results for the three uncapped and five capped specimens that were loaded in tension-tension fatigue, along with those for the static tension tests, are plotted on a load versus number of cycles curve in Figure 5. The average static tension failure load of the four uncapped specimens was 8.10 kN (1,808 lb). The failure loads of the specimens varied widely over a range of 6.19 to 10.09 kN (1,380 to 2,250 lb) with a coefficient of variation of 24%. The three capped specimens failed at an average load of 19.6 kN (4,367 lb). The highest failure load attained was 20.8 kN (4,650 lb), the lowest was 17.7 kN (3,950 lb), and the coefficient of variation was only 8%. The lines in the fatigue curve are the straight-line, least-squares fits of the data points. The loads corresponding to 10,000 loading cycles — 6.28 kN (1,400 lb) for the uncapped specimens and 14.2 kN (3,160 lb) for the capped specimens — are obtained from the least-squares fits. The strength increase from the unreinforced to the reinforced specimens is almost the same for 10,000 cycles (about 130%) as for the static tests (about 140%).

Figure 5 Fatigue Behavior of U-Shaped-Cap-Reinforced and Unreinforced Graphite-Epoxy Laminates

Different failure modes occur for uncapped versus capped specimens. The failed uncapped specimens have extensive delamination along the free edge that extends throughout the entire plane of the specimen. Moreover, they fail along directions parallel to the fibers. No fiber breakage is evident in the uncapped specimens. In sharp contrast, the failed capped specimens have obvious broken graphite fibers in the $\pm 30^\circ$ layers without any significant delamination.

Recent comparisons of theory and experiment [6] have revealed that early results for edge-cap reinforcement, i.e., Reference [5], were obtained with laminates made of graphite-epoxy prepregged material that was about ten years old - far beyond the normal allowed storage life in engineering practice. Accordingly, the aged epoxy material did not cross-link as effectively in the curing process as does "fresh" epoxy. The basic result of the extended storage is that the uncapped laminates were so degraded in matrix properties that good bonding between laminae could not be achieved. Thus, the static strength and fatigue strength of uncapped laminates at a prescribed number of fatigue cycles were much lower than obtained with relatively fresh material as seen in Figure 6. The effect of putting edge caps on a laminate having "old" matrix material was to prevent the strong delamination tendency and bring the laminate up to the strength and life level it would have had if the matrix material had been fresh. Thus, the high strength increases reported in [5] would not be expected in practice. However, the unexpected effective updating of the old matrix material might have some interesting practical applications.

Figure 6 Effect of Matrix Age on Fatigue Behavior of Uncapped Graphite-Epoxy Laminates

Edge caps with fibers in an $[0^\circ/90^\circ]$ orientation are more effective than caps with fibers in a $[\pm 45^\circ]$ orientation as seen in Figure 7 [7]. The interlaminar normal stress is the dominant local loading near the edge, and the vertical fibers in the $[0^\circ/90^\circ]$ cap resist that stress with high strength. However, the $[\pm 45^\circ]$ caps do not have any fibers in the direction of the predominant loading, so their strength is lower and hence their reinforcement capability is less than $[0^\circ/90^\circ]$ caps. The $[\pm 45^\circ]$ caps are initially attractive because of their tendency to clamp down on the laminate when it is subjected to tension load as in the Chinese finger torture device. However, that high effective Poisson's ratio effect is only a stiffness effect that is severely limited in practical applications by the extremely low strength of cloth in the across-the-bias direction. Under static load, single-layered bias-oriented caps actually decrease strength by 2% from the uncapped baseline laminate strength whereas, from results not shown, static strength increases by 5% with double-layered bias-oriented caps and by 23% with triple-layered bias-oriented edge caps [7].

Figure 7 Fatigue Behavior of Graphite-Epoxy Laminates with $[0^\circ/90^\circ]$ and $[\pm 45^\circ]$ Kevlar-Epoxy Edge Caps

2.2 Effect of Interleaved Adhesive Layers Another free-edge reinforcement concept is to add extra adhesive material in sheet form between the composite laminae to provide a region of highly deformable material near the inherent material and geometric discontinuities that exist at the laminae boundaries [8]. The adhesive layers need be provided only in a narrow boundary layer near the free edges. However, special tooling would be required to restrict the adhesive to that boundary-layer region. For simplicity and in the spirit of merely demonstrating a point, the adhesive layers were applied over the entire area of the 38 mm by 180 mm (1-1/2" by 7") specimens. Naturally, the 40% increased weight of such specimens far exceeds what would be used in a practical application of this concept. The resulting performance for laminates with interleaved adhesive layers is an increase in static failure load of 40% and in fatigue strength at 10,000 cycles of 36% over laminates without adhesive layers as shown in Figure 8 [8].

Figure 8 Fatigue Behavior of Graphite-Epoxy Laminates with and without Interleaved Adhesive Layers

Other success with adhesive layers is reported by Chan, Rogers, and Aker [9]. Adhesive layers would be expected to be attractive for laminates in which interlaminar shear stresses play a big role in free-edge delamination. If the interlaminar normal stress dominates the free-edge delamination of a specific laminate, then the inherent weakness in tension of adhesive layers would preclude their use in that laminate.

2.3 Effect of Edge Stitching Stitching seems like a very natural way to strengthen a laminate by putting fibers in a direction where none exist. However, some results by Mignery, Tan, and Sun led to the conclusion that stitching might harm laminates by breaking the in-plane fibers during the mechanical stitching process [10]. For axially loaded specimens with a single stitch line of Kevlar thread next to each free edge as in Figure 4, static loading results for onset of delamination and failure [10] are shown in Figure 9 for three types of AS4-3501-6 graphite-epoxy laminates: $[\pm 30/0]_S$ (fiber-dominated); $[\pm 30/90]_S$ (matrix-dominated); and $[\pm 45/0_2/90_2]_S$ (not dominated). There, stitching nearly always raises the stress at onset of delamination, but does not always raise the stress at failure. Specimen edges were coated with white paint to readily enable visual delamination detection. Note that the $[\pm 30/0]_S$ (fiber-dominated) laminates did not exhibit delamination, even when not stitched. Mignery, Tan, and Sun used dye-penetrant techniques and X-radiographs to demonstrate that edge delaminations are arrested at the stitching line. Their results are for the case in which *preimpregnated* fiber systems are stitched. In that case, the in-plane fibers tend to be held in place by the uncured matrix material and thereby are susceptible to damage because the fibers cannot move out of the way of the penetrating needle. They also developed a finite element model of a stitched laminate and were able to determine that the through-the-thickness stress, σ_z , is not reduced unless the stitch line is impractically close to the free edge. Stitching does reduce the strain-energy-release rate as the delamination approaches the stitch line.

In contrast, the more contemporary approach for stitching is to stitch an unimpregnated fabric or unidirectional fiber layer that has relatively flimsy crossing fibers interwoven to hold the major unidirectional fibers in approximate position. In this new approach, the major fibers can easily be pushed aside by the stitching needle so are less susceptible to damage during the stitching process than are the preimpregnated fiber systems. Then, after stitching, the stitched fiber systems are impregnated by resin transfer molding. Results for this condition will be reported by Jones for both static and fatigue loading at a later date.

Figure 9 Static Delamination and Failure Results for Preimpregnated Stitched Laminates [10]

2.4 Effect of Ply Termination A laminate free edge can be modified by changing the laminate stacking sequence only in the immediate vicinity of the free edge by terminating a troublesome ply several laminate thicknesses away from the free edge as in Figure 4. This approach is sometimes called tapering, but that term is more suitable for the machined-edge laminate in Figure 4. The term ply termination, or, more colloquially, ply drop-off, is used herein. Chan and Ochoa reported results for an interlaminar-normal-stress-dominated $[30/ - 30_2/30/90]_S$ laminate cycled at 179 MPa (25.93 ksi) (90% of the average stress at static onset of delamination of the baseline laminates without ply termination) in Table 1 [11]. There, the static strength and fatigue life were substantially increased by terminating the 90° plies. Moreover, for those laminates with ply termination, no delamination occurred in either static or fatigue loading. For those laminates without ply termination that delaminated, the residual strength was significantly increased by use of ply termination.

LAMINATE	CYCLES 10^6	FATIGUE DAMAGE	RESIDUAL STRENGTH MPa	STATIC STRENGTH MPa
WITHOUT PLY TERMINATION	5.602	FINAL FAILURE	-	-
	6.000	DELAMINATION	444	451
	4.691	FINAL FAILURE	-	-
WITH PLY TERMINATION	9.000	NO DELAMINATION	568	
	9.000	NO DELAMINATION	584	
	9.000	NO DELAMINATION	555	

Table 1 Fatigue Loading Results for $[30/ - 30_2/30/90]_S$ Laminates with and without Ply Termination [11]

2.5 Effect of Edge Notching A second method of laminate-free-edge modification is edge notching where the edge is cut many times with a narrow cutting wheel resulting in the notched edge shown in Figure 4. Sun and Chu reported static loading results for ten different combinations of notch size and spacing on the behavior of laminates with delamination caused by interlaminar normal stress and alternatively by interlaminar shear stress [12]. The notches must be sufficiently close to each other to force laminate failure by stress concentration as opposed to the free-edge effect. For off-axis loading of an interlaminar-shear-controlled $[0/90/\pm 45]_S$ laminate, (1) notched laminates are always stronger than unnotched laminates by about 20% for 7.5° off-axis loading and by about 30% for 15° off-axis loading; (2) notched laminates have lower strengths than unnotched laminates if loaded at 0° to the laminate reference axis; and (3) no difference in performance could be detected between the ten notch types (different notch widths, depths, and spacings). Under the off-axis loading, the notched quasi-isotropic laminate tends to exhibit nearly constant strength as a function of off-axis loading angle. In contrast, the strength of an unnotched quasi-isotropic laminate drops off significantly under off-axis loading. For laminates dominated by interlaminar normal stress as in Table 2, the static failure load is always reduced by notching (an obviously undesirable effect if taken by itself), but none of the notched laminates delaminated! That is, the notching concept is used to suppress delamination by confusing the stress field in the free-edge boundary layer. The objective is not necessarily to increase static strength, but the principal benefit of notching is to suppress delamination and thereby presumably increase fatigue life by eliminating the delamination that would otherwise be expected to limit fatigue life. The author will soon report fatigue results to address that hypothesis and whether notch type affects fatigue results. The strength of notched laminates is perhaps affected by stress concentrations at the notches. However, our interest is only in the gross result of delamination suppression.

LAMINATE	NOTCH TYPE	DELAMINATION LOAD (kN/m)	FAILURE LOAD (kN/m)
[±45/0/90] _S	UNNOTCHED	388	611
	NOTCHED*	-	570
[±45/90/0] _S	UNNOTCHED	397	652
	NOTCHED*	-	635
[0/±45/90] _S	UNNOTCHED	418	679
	NOTCHED*	-	612
[±45/0 ₂ /90 ₂] _S	UNNOTCHED	618	1135
	NOTCHED*	-	1110

*Average of Two Notch Styles

Table 2 Static Loading Results for Laminates Dominated by Interlaminar Normal Stress (Opening Mode Delamination) [12]

3. CONCLUDING REMARKS

The following conclusions are reached from the reported experimental results.

1. Edge Caps:
 - a. Edge caps delay in-plane delamination, increase static strength, and increase fatigue life in a relatively easy-to-make process.
 - b. The influence of a single layer as one layer of an eleven-layer laminate is quite small (9%), but the effect of the edge cap is to increase the failure load by far, far more than 9%. Thus, the real influence of the cap is to restrain free-edge delamination, i.e., the failure mode changes. Thus, addition of a cap is quite unlike the addition of merely another layer of material.
 - c. Fiber orientation in an edge cap is important. If cloth is placed in a [±45°] orientation, the edge is compressed more during axial tension loading than with a [0°/90°] orientation, but the latter orientation is much stronger.
2. Interleaved Adhesive Layers:
 - a. Require special tooling near the edges to make.
 - b. The main benefit is increased static strength and fatigue life.
3. Edge Stitching:
 - a. Arrests delamination at the stitch line
 - b. Does not always affect static strength
 - c. No fatigue results available
4. Ply Termination:
 - a. Suppresses delamination
 - b. Increases static strength and fatigue life.
5. Edge Notching:
 - a. Suppresses delamination
 - b. Both increases and decreases static strength, depending on the laminate.
 - c. No fatigue results available

Special laminates were used in this study because of their strong tendency to delaminate. Thus, the strength increases shown herein cannot be expected for general laminates. However, the concepts can be applied to practical structures with significant benefits. Some delamination-suppression concepts still have not been investigated under the practically important case of fatigue loading. Experiments are underway to determine that behavior.

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